

IS THE ABILITY TO PAY PRINCIPLE ETHICALLY BANKRUPT?

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Abstract

This article critically examines the ability to pay premise from an ethical perspective. The author finds the ability to pay principle to be ethically bankrupt whether one takes a utilitarian or rights approach to ethics.

Introduction

The ability to pay principle "maintains that taxes should be distributed according to the capacity of taxpayers to pay them."² This principle has been justified on several grounds over the years. A dollar taken from a rich man reduces total utility less than does a dollar taken from a poor man, or so the saying goes. The problem with this philosophical approach is that a closer analysis reveals

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² DAVID N. HYMAN, PUBLIC FINANCE: A CONTEMPORARY APPLICATION OF THEORY TO POLICY 663 (6th ed. 1999). Adam Smith's first Canon of taxation was that individuals should contribute "as nearly as possible in proportion to their respective abilities." ADAM SMITH, THE WEALTH OF NATIONS 310 (1776; 1937), as quoted in JOHN CULLIS AND PHILIP JONES, PUBLIC FINANCE AND PUBLIC CHOICE 244 (1998). Rosen defines ability to pay as the "Capacity to pay a tax, which may be measured by income, consumption, or wealth." HARVEY S. ROSEN, PUBLIC FINANCE 529 (5TH ED. 1999).

that "progressive taxation cannot be justified by reference to the principle of diminishing marginal utility of income."³

Several philosophical approaches may be taken to determine whether the ability to pay principle is ethically sound. Utilitarianism is one. Rights is another. We shall examine both.

The Utilitarian Approach

Utilitarianism is a kind of ethical philosophy, an approach to making moral judgments. There are several ways to look at utilitarianism. Some utilitarians would say that a policy is good, just and ethical if it results in the greatest good for the greatest number. Other utilitarians would say that a policy is good if its implementation would result in increasing total utility. Economists would say that a policy is good if it results in a positive-sum game, where the winners exceed the losers. Jeremy Bentham would say that human suffering and enjoyment are the only sources of right and wrong.⁴ Where the amount of pleasure exceeds the amount of pain, the action is ethical. If total pain exceeds total pleasure, the action or policy is unethical.

³ RICHARD A. POSNER, *ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF LAW* 547 (5TH ED. 1998). Posner's Chapter 16: Income Inequalities, Distributive Justice, and Poverty 497-521 completely destroys the notion that the ability to pay concept can be justified on marginal utility grounds. For an exposition of the now discarded theory that total utility can be increased if the rich nations would give money to poor nations, see RUBEN P. MENDEZ, *INTERNATIONAL PUBLIC FINANCE: A NEW PERSPECTIVE ON GLOBAL RELATIONS* 104-5 (1992).

⁴ WILLIAM H. SHAW, *CONTEMPORARY ETHICS: TAKING ACCOUNT OF UTILITARIANISM* 69(1999), citing Bentham's *The rationale of judicial evidence, specially applied to English practice*, in *THE WORKS OF JEREMY BENTHAM*, vol. 6, ed. J. Bowring (1962), at 238. For a defense of utilitarianism, see SHAW at 68-101. For objections to utilitarianism, see SHAW, 102-132. For refutations of the utilitarian ethic, see MURRAY N. ROTHBARD, *MAN, ECONOMY, AND STATE* 260-268 (1970); Robert W. McGee, *The Fatal Flaw in the Methodology of Law & Economics*, *COMMENTARIES ON LAW & ECONOMICS* 209-223 (1997); Robert W. McGee, *The Fatal Flaw in NAFTA, GATT and All Other Trade Agreements*, *14 NORTHWESTERN JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL LAW & BUSINESS* 549-565 (1994).

The utilitarian ethic has been applied to the philosophy of public finance in an attempt to determine the optimal tax policy. For example,

The real income ... after any taxes should be equal, except (a) for supplements to meet special needs, (b) supplements recompensing services to the extent needed to provide desirable incentive and allocate resources efficiently, and (c) variations to achieve other socially desirable ends such as population control.⁵

Economists almost universally subscribe to utilitarian ethics. Economists are wealth maximizers. A policy is good if it increases wealth and best if it maximizes wealth. They would argue that there is no inconsistency between morality and efficiency.⁶

If we accept the premise that what is efficient is also moral,⁷ we run into ethical problems with the ability to pay principle because it is inefficient. Economists have given a number of utilitarian reasons against the graduated income tax.⁸ For one thing, it destroys the incentive of the most productive people. And since it is primarily the most productive people who save, invest and create jobs, a graduated tax will retard economic growth by reducing the amount of capital available for investment.

A progressive tax system, which is the kind of tax system one has if one begins with the premise that the tax system should

⁵ RICHARD B. BRANDT, *A THEORY OF THE GOOD AND THE RIGHT* 310 (1979), as cited by SHAW, *supra*, at 235.

⁶ RICHARD A. POSNER, *ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF LAW* 546 (5TH ED. 1998).

⁷ There are a number of problems with the premise that what is efficient is moral but we will leave discussion of this issue for another day.

⁸ For examples, see WALTER J. BLUM AND HARRY KALVEN, JR., *THE UNEASY CASE FOR PROGRESSIVE TAXATION* (1953); F.A. Hayek, *The Case Against Progressive Income Taxes*, *THE FREEMAN* 229-32 (December 28, 1953).

be based on the ability to pay, causes the inefficient substitution of leisure for work because it increases the price of work relative to that of leisure.⁹ A progressive tax also decreases the amount of risk taking relative to that that would take place where the tax system is not progressive.¹⁰ As risk taking is reduced, so is income mobility. Aversion to risk taking can have an adverse effect on economic growth, capital accumulation and expansion of employment.

There are also social costs of having a progressive tax system. People who are in a high tax bracket will find it profitable to pay accountants and attorneys huge sums to reduce their tax liability.¹¹ Someone who owes \$100,000 in taxes should logically be willing to pay an accountant or an attorney up to \$99,999 to find ways to avoid the tax. This money could better be spent on investment in some project that generates income and creates employment rather than being diverted in defense of retaining property that the tax collector would otherwise take. A large chunk of the U.S. Internal Revenue Code exists solely to prevent people from finding ways around the progressivity of the income tax.¹²

Countries that have adopted a progressive tax system tend to have highly complex tax systems with multiple rates, numerous exemptions, etc. These complications greatly decrease the efficiency of tax collection.¹³ Complex tax systems also cost billions of dollars in administration costs. According to one

⁹ POSNER, *supra*, at 544.

¹⁰ POSNER, *supra*, at 545.

¹¹ POSNER, *supra*, at 545-546.

¹² RICHARD A. EPSTEIN, SIMPLE RULES FOR A COMPLEX WORLD 147(1995).

¹³ Robert W. McGee, *Taxation and Public Finance: A Philosophical and Ethical Approach*, COMMENTARIES ON THE LAW OF ACCOUNTING & FINANCE 157-240 (1997); Robert W. McGee, *Tax Advice for Latvia and Other Similarly Situated Emerging Economies*, 13 INTERNATIONAL TAX & BUSINESS LAWYER 223-308 (1996); Robert W. McGee, *Principles of Taxation for Emerging Economies: Some Lessons from the U.S. Experience*, 12 DICKINSON JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL LAW 29-93 (1993).

estimate, the cost of administering the federal tax system in the United States is \$600 billion.¹⁴

Another inefficiency with a graduated tax system is that it increases animosity between the rich and the poor. It is divisive in the sense that it forces high income earners to pay what might be perceived to be more than their "fair share" of the tax burden. And it exacerbates the envy that the lower income earners already have toward high-income earners.¹⁵ Thus, it decreases social harmony and stability.

One might argue that it is only fair that the rich pay more in total than the poor do, because the rich have more property to protect than the poor do. Since protecting property is a function of government, it seems only fair that those who have more property will pay more, in total, for government services than those who own less property. This line of reasoning seems reasonable on the surface. But if one digs beneath the surface, problems start to appear with this line of reasoning. For one thing, there may be little or no relationship between the cost of protecting property and the amount of property to be protected. It may cost more to protect 100 acres of land worth \$10,000 than to protect a bank vault that contains \$100 million.¹⁶ One might logically argue that if it costs 10% more to protect the property of someone who earns \$1 million a year than someone who earns \$10,000 a year, then one might conclude that the person with the \$1 million income should pay 10% more in taxes than the person who earns \$10,000. Critics of this approach would be quick to claim that such a tax system is "regressive," as though there is something somehow wrong with regressivity.

¹⁴ James L. Payne, *Unhappy Returns: The \$600-Billion Tax Ripoff*, POLICY REVIEW 21 (Winter 1992).

¹⁵ HELMUT SCHOECK, ENVY: A THEORY OF SOCIAL BEHAVIOR 194, 217, 221 (1966); ROBERT SHEAFFER, RESENTMENT AGAINST ACHIEVEMENT: UNDERSTANDING THE ASSAULT UPON ABILITY 177, 186 (1988).

¹⁶ Murray N. Rothbard makes this point at 115 in POWER AND MARKET: GOVERNMENT AND THE ECONOMY (1970).

The ability to pay principle does not stand up to utilitarian ethical analysis because it is inefficient and thus unethical. However, the utilitarian approach to ethics suffers from at least two major weaknesses: (1) There is no accurate or precise way to measure gains and losses and (2) utilitarian ethics totally ignores rights.¹⁷

Even though a utilitarian approach makes it easy to see that the ability to pay principle leads to inefficiency, and is thus unethical from a utilitarian perspective, it is not possible to measure the degree of inefficiency. Also, as was mentioned, the utilitarian approach to ethics is defective because it ignores rights.

The Rights Approach

The rights approach avoids the two flaws inherent in utilitarianism. If one begins with the premise that an action is unethical if one person's rights are violated, there is no need to measure gains and losses but only to determine whether one person's rights have been violated. A utilitarian would conclude that an action is ethical even though someone's rights might be violated as long as there are more winners than losers or as long as the good exceeds the bad and that is the inherent flaw in the utilitarian approach.

In a progressive tax system, those who have more are exploited by those who have less. There is an inherent injustice in such a system because some people are living at the expense of others. Individuals are being treated as means rather than as ends in themselves. One might say that the family is based on this system - where some (children) live at the expense of others (parents) -- but this analogy is inapplicable if for no other reason than the fact

¹⁷ I could have said that utilitarian ethics totally ignores "individual" rights but there is no need to include the word "individual" when speaking about rights since individual rights are the only kind of rights that exist. There is no such thing as group rights.

that the family is a voluntary association whereas the tax system is based on coercion.¹⁸

An Overlooked Philosophical Point

There are two basic and diametrically opposed views of taxation. Those who favor the ability to pay approach view the state as a master, who extracts tribute from its subjects on the basis of how much they are able to pay. Those who take this first approach often also view the state as a benevolent father figure, who distributes tax benefits on the basis of need. In Karl Marx's words, "From each according to his abilities; to each according to his needs."¹⁹

Those who take the service provider approach view the state as the servant of the people. Government provides services and taxpayers pay for the services. Those who benefit the most from the services should pay the most. And those who do not use a particular government service²⁰ should not be forced to pay for it at all.²¹ Thomas Cooley makes the following point:

¹⁸ We will leave for another day a discussion of whether any tax can be just, since all taxes seemingly violate the right to property. However, this topic has already been discussed elsewhere. For examples, see Robert W. McGee, *Is Tax Evasion Unethical?* 42 UNIVERSITY OF KANSAS LAW REVIEW 411-435 (Winter 1994); Robert W. McGee, *Should Accountants be Punished for Aiding and Abetting Tax Evasion?* 1 *Journal of Accounting, Ethics & Public Policy* 16-44 (Winter 1998); Walter Block, *The Justification for Taxation in the Economics Literature*, 36 CANADIAN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION/ADMINISTRATION PUBLIQUE DU CANADA 225-262 (Summer/Été 1993), 225-262, revised and reprinted in THE ETHICS OF TAX EVASION (ROBERT W. MCGEE, ED. 1998), at 36-88.

¹⁹ Karl Marx, Critique of the Gotha Program (1875). The original wording was "Jeder nach seinen Fähigkeiten, jedem nach seinen Bedürfnissen." Louis Blanc, the French socialist, said basically the same thing in 1848. George Seldes, *The Great Thoughts* 274 (1985).

²⁰ The excise tax on gasoline is an example of the application of the benefit principle. Those who use roads pay a gasoline tax, which is supposed to cover the cost of maintaining the roads. However, not all excise taxes are tied in to benefits received. For example, if the amount of excise tax charged for gasoline is five or ten times the cost of maintaining the roads, it ceases to be a tax that is tied in to benefits. Some excise taxes, like those on alcohol and tobacco, are

Taxation is the equivalent for the protection which the government affords to the person and property of its citizens; and as all alike are protected, so all alike should bear the burden, in proportion to the interests secured.²²

A corollary to the service provider approach is that there should be some maximum tax,²³ an amount above which no one should have to pay. Leona Helmsley, for example, who went to prison for tax evasion,²⁴ would not have been punished if the U.S. tax system were set up under a service provider principle because the amount of taxes she paid -- more than \$100 million -- exceeded the benefit she received. Under the service provider principle she would have been entitled to a refund. But because she paid a few million dollars less than she "owed" under the graduated, ability to pay system, and because she resorted to illegal means to prevent the government from assessing the "proper" amount, she was sentenced to prison. It is difficult to believe that she received more than \$100 million in services from the federal government over the

punitive in nature. Such punitive taxes have no place in a society where government is supposed to be the servant rather than the master. For a discussion of the abuse of excise taxes, see *TAXING CHOICE: THE PREDATORY POLITICS OF FISCAL DISCRIMINATION* (WILLIAM F. SHUGHART II, ED. 1997).

²¹ There are problems with both of these approaches. There is no way to objectively determine what someone's ability to pay is, so it must be decided arbitrarily. And there is no way to determine how much benefit someone receives from government services that are made available even if few people want them, since the price of such services is determined by bureaucratic fiat rather than through voluntary exchange.

²² THOMAS COOLEY, *CONSTITUTIONAL LIMITATIONS* 613 (5TH ED. 1883), as quoted in RICHARD A. EPSTEIN, *PRINCIPLES FOR A FREE SOCIETY: RECONCILING INDIVIDUAL LIBERTY WITH THE COMMON GOOD* 129 (1998).

²³ For more on the concept of a maximum tax, see Robert W. McGee, *The Case for a Maximum Tax: A Look at Some Legal, Economic and Ethical Issues*, 1 *JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY* 294-299 (Spring 1998).

²⁴ *U.S. v. Helmsley*, 733 F.Supp. 600, 941 F.2d 71 (2nd Cir. 1991).

years. It seems like a clear case of the government exploiting one of its more productive citizens.²⁵

Concluding Comments

The ability to pay principle involves exploitation. The government exploits the producers -- the wealth creators -- and redistributes a portion of their income to wealth consumers -- those who use the various government programs. In that sense, it is a parasitical system. The service provider principle, on the other hand, attempts to match costs with benefits. Those who use government services pay for them, and those who do not use the services are not forced to pay. Thus, the service provider principle is fairer than the ability to pay principle because it is based on principles of equity rather than exploitation. So a tax that is based on the service provider principle is to be preferred to a tax that relies on the ability to pay principle, all other things being equal.

However, it should be pointed out that both taxes raised under the ability to pay principle and under the service provider approach are generally raised by the use of force or the threat of force, except in the case where the method used is a user fee or lottery. So both methods suffers from defects, although the service provider approach at least attempts to match costs and benefits equitably, whereas the ability to pay concept makes no such attempts.

²⁵ Ross Perot, during one of the televised U.S. presidential debates in October, 1992, announced that he has paid \$1 billion in taxes over the years. One must wonder how the federal government could possibly provide him with \$1 billion in services. It seems unlikely that he could get his moneysworth even if the government provided him with a large home, free clothing and ten meals a day. But he makes too much money to even qualify for welfare, so he is not able to get food or housing from the government.